

How SPATRA Works

SPATRA integrates multiple data sources into one system:

- Copernicus EO data
- Galileo/EGNSS for authenticated positioning
- Drone-based RGB and thermal imaging
- In-situ data from vehicles and sensors
- Processing pipelines on a cloud-based platform

The system produces real-time dashboards, alerts, and prediction results useful for logistics planning and rail network operations.

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SPACE-BASED APPLICATIONS FOR TRANSPORT MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT

Transforming Transportation:
 Navigating Challenges, Embracing
 Innovation for an Efficient, Safe,
 and Sustainable Future

SPATRA Consortium

About the Project

SPATRA develops downstream applications for **road and rail transport** based on Copernicus and EGNSS services. The project focuses on two challenges:

- **Road traffic** congestion and limited parking availability for freight vehicles
- Extreme heat impact on **rail infrastructure** and risk of rail buckling

SPATRA brings satellite imagery, geolocation services, drones, and local measurements into practical tools that support transport operators, logistics companies, and railway infrastructure managers.

Road Transport Application

SPATRA uses **Sentinel-2 data**, **EGNSS**, and **drone** imagery to detect trucks, identify congestion, and estimate parking availability. Combining satellite images, drone photos, and in-situ location data improves **route planning** and **arrival-time predictions**.

Pilot site

- Border-crossing **Horgoš (Serbia–Hungary)**, supported by logistics company **Nelt**.

Rail Transport Application

SPATRA combines **Copernicus land-surface temperature data**, **Sentinel-2 indices**, **local measurements**, and **drone thermal** images to map heat exposure along rail tracks. This enables prediction of **rail temperature** and **early warnings** for rail-buckling risk.

Pilot site

- The pilot is supported by **Serbian Railway Infrastructure**.